

CHANGES IN DIGITAL MARKETING IN MODERN REALITY

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Аннотация. Цель данной статьи – выявить основные изменения, с которыми может столкнуться цифровой маркетинг в современное время. Некоторые проекты уже успели прочувствовать на себе насколько важно быть к ним готовым и уметь адаптироваться. Путем анализа известных источников, коммуникации с создателями инфопродуктов и персональных наблюдений удалось выявить самые распространенные, которые и будут рассмотрены в данной статье.

Ключевые слова: кризис, цифровой маркетинг, социальные сети, путь клиента, решение о покупке, лояльность, реклама, инфлюенсеры.

Abstract. The purpose of this article is to identify the main changes that digital marketing may face in modern times. Some projects have already felt how important it is to be prepared for them and to be able to adapt. By analyzing well-known sources, communicating with creators of information products, and personal observations, the most common changes have been identified, which will be discussed in this article.

Keywords: crisis, digital marketing, social networks, customer journey, purchase decision, loyalty, advertising, influencers.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi zamonaviy vaqtlarda raqamli marketingda yuz beradigan asosiy o'zgarishlarni aniqlashdir. Ba'zi loyihalar ularning qanchalik muhimligini his qilgan va ularga moslashish qobiliyatini rivojlantirgan. Mashhur manbalarni tahlil qilib, axborot mahsulotlari yaratuvchilari bilan muloqot qilib va shaxsiy kuzatishlar orqali eng ko'p uchraydigan o'zgarishlar aniqlangan bo'lib, bu maqolada ular muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: inqiroz, raqamli marketing, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, mijoz yo'li, xarid qarori, sodiqlik, reklama, ta'sirchilar.

As it is well known, marketing is characterized by numerous directions. Each of them can be called indispensable in its own way, as they are united by common goals such as increasing profitability and brand awareness, as well as enhancing customer loyalty. However, depending on the time period, certain directions have become increasingly popular and more profitable. In modern times, the most vivid example is digital marketing. Digital marketing is based on the same traditional marketing principles that professionals implement through digital communication channels. For example, this can include advertisements that we see daily on social media and websites. The application of digital marketing tools can be observed when viewers in an online cinema are offered to follow social media accounts to participate in a contest or scan a QR code to win a prize.

However, digital marketing, even before it fully popularized, has already undergone numerous changes. For instance, the years 2020-2021 can be characterized as an ideal time for targeted advertising and SMM (social media marketing). Tools that users had not yet grown tired of enjoyed incredible success, so companies were always attentive to such changes to timely implement them as branches of their marketing strategy. For social media audiences, everything

was new, and consequently, sales occurred with just a few touches. It is worth noting that COVID-19 made a significant contribution here, leading to a global surge in purchases of information products, with demand exceeding supply. In 2022-2023, there was active development in digital marketing, where old methods still worked; it was just necessary to be smarter and faster, as well as stand out with creativity. During this period, there was also a noticeable jump in prices, as a high average check was seen as a sign of quality. By 2024, there was an active decline due to accumulated consumer experience, the uniformity of methods and strategies, and an oversaturation of advertising. Numerous purchases led to the formation of "immunity" to new emerging offers. Hence arises the question: what will we face in 2025?

As mentioned above, negative consumer experiences, crises and instability in the external world have created new obstacles for marketers. Despite this, the main component in developing a promotional marketing strategy remains the Customer Journey Map (CJM) which allows for planning the customer's path, adding additional touchpoints and providing necessary information or triggers at moments when they may be critically needed. Thus, while the standard path previously consisted of six touchpoints, it now sometimes reaches up to 30 touchpoints from the moment of product acquaintance before a final purchasing decision is made in certain sectors. Such changes are particularly inevitable for products with a high average check due to extreme buyer caution. If we return to the moment of first contact – how the acquaintance with the product occurs – it can be noted that attracting new customers is becoming increasingly expensive while their quality and loyalty diminish day by day. Based on this, the following points will examine the problems faced by the market (in the digital sphere) in 2025.

It has become much harder to influence consumers and motivate them to make purchases online. This is because the primary purpose of using social media for many people is now to get a quick dopamine hit to relax. Consequently, the brain is working minimally, and it actively refuses to absorb advertising or any content aimed at sales [1].

Nowadays, there is also a strong need for more detailed work with cold audiences, as well as personalization of their journey depending on the channels they came from. The channels used to ensure a steady flow of customers differ in their index of established need: some have already studied information about the product while others have only been hooked by a headline in an advertisement. Here, it is paramount to provide them with information to further advance them along Ben Hunt's Awareness Ladder.

For example, for someone who has clicked through to your social media page after realizing that the headline in the ad resonates with them, it will be necessary to explain what you offer and why it is beneficial for them to stay with you. The word "beneficial" can also mean the fact that buying or further progressing along your path costs less than the opportunity they stand to miss. This highlights the importance of a deep understanding of your target audience, their needs and their expectations.

Another important point is that emotional purchases have become less frequent and harder to provoke due to negative consumer experiences. Today, people find it more difficult to trust what they see online. Upon encountering a new offer, instead of making an immediate purchase, they will start researching alternatives or ask their friends and so on.

In early 2025, we can already observe a decline in the influence of the major social media influencers. This is manifested in the fact that users are less likely to buy based solely on a personality. They have become more concerned with what they are buying and how the purchase will help them in modern life. In its turn, this tells us about the decreasing effectiveness of influencer marketing. Potential customers will not blindly follow a blogger's advice and

therefore, when using this type of marketing, you need to take care to present the product by the personality and carefully work on the advertising copy. When choosing a personality with whom to collaborate, it is important to rely on the similarity of the values transmitted with your brand and on the quality of the audience.

It is well known, the market is saturated with techniques, which have led to a loss of effectiveness in aggressive sales. Aggressive sales are understood as motivating purchases by highlighting the pain points of the target audience and subsequently applying additional pressure on them. The significant decline in their effectiveness has been largely influenced by the popularization of psychotherapy. More and more people are turning to psychologists to alleviate anxiety, establish personal boundaries and so on. Consequently, the aforementioned techniques in advertising and other forms of communication with clients evoke distrust and repel potential customers. From a modern perspective such "aggressive sales" are perceived as a potential threat to one's well-being which individuals have spent a long time achieving or are still striving for. As a result, people have stopped succumbing to pressure and have begun seeking solutions that can be provided through more eco-friendly methods.

With increasing competition in the market, positioning has become an indispensable element for all companies to remain viable. Skillfully identifying competitive advantages and highlighting them in the most favorable way at early stages can be equated to guaranteed success. Currently there is still a trend of increasing competition and companies and entrepreneurs are striving to stand out more in the market trying to differentiate themselves from numerous competitors. However, the greater the number of offerings, the harder it becomes to create a truly unique proposition. This phenomenon ultimately leads companies to absurd differentiations that are not perceived by consumers due to the use of exotic concepts rather than solid meanings [2].

The oversaturation of advertising observed on the Internet and social media makes it increasingly difficult to overcome banner blindness. Advertisers continue to use familiar images and slogans that fail to generate interest in the product. As a result, managers are forced to increase promotion costs which can negatively impact the development of newly established companies. However, when an advertising campaign is successful and people take further action as called for in your advertisement, one may encounter the next problem – lack of or minimal conversion into purchases. The main explanation for this phenomenon is that interaction ends after viewing the advertisement and there is no further engagement with potential customers. This is precisely why it is very easy to lose new potential clients [3].

An important change is the shift in users' perception of success and an above-average lifestyle which no longer attract attention or generate excitement for purchases. For example, travel and tourism were often associated with the luxury segment and seen as a sign that a frequently traveling person is successful in life. Today, this approach is hard to call effective that is why some travel agencies are shifting their focus to the accessibility of travel and its necessity in everyone's life, emphasizing how it helps people relax and escape from routine. This has led to the popularization of authentic destinations such as "retreats," "camps" for adults and trips to nature. Of course, classic destinations still enjoy sufficient demand, but they are no longer perceived to the same extent as luxury elements such as Bali, the Maldives or Dubai.

In conclusion, we can highlight the main aspects that are priorities in digital marketing: working with the customer base – those who are already familiar with the products/services. Companies should strive not to attract new customers each time but, on the contrary, to form a stable customer base that will be loyal to them. All components of the 12P concept should be

developed at a high level. Additionally, managing the product line becomes crucial so that it can generate new profits from existing customers, thereby creating a product funnel. Furthermore, in a world where instability is increasingly noticeable, marketers in 2025 need to work with established human habits and routines that bring stability to our lives and often dictate our consumer choices.

Thus, it can be asserted that the modern market is undergoing significant changes; some may argue that these changes are related to a possible crisis in the digital sphere. Accordingly, digital marketing needs to apply and invent new techniques and adapt old ones.

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